

A Review of Failure Mechanism of Pile-supported Structures due to Earthquake Induced Soil Liquefaction

Review Paper

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ABSTRACT

The paper reviews the failure mechanism of pile-supported structures in liquefiable soil during earthquakes. Post-earthquake investigation of many pile-supported structures on liquefiable soil shows that despite the large factor of safety against bending due to lateral loads employed in their design, structures failed, e.g. failure of firehouse building at Kobe Port in 1995, Japan. It has also been observed that the middle piers of the bridges collapsed without significantly affecting the other parts. A number of experiments conducted by various investigators highlighted the importance of pile failure modes other than bending mechanism, especially, pile failure due to buckling. The initial codes of practice for pile design on liquefiable soils such as NEHRP 2000, Eurocode 8, JRA1996, and IS1893 focused only on bending failure, and failure due to buckling/dynamic amplification of pile due to the axial loading during liquefaction was neglected.

Keywords: *Pile failure, liquefiable soil, bending, buckling, shear, dynamic amplification*

INTRODUCTION

Pile foundations are most widely used deep foundation especially in case of saturated cohesionless soil, which is susceptible to liquefaction during an earthquake. Due to the rise in global population and limited land resources, infrastructures are often constructed over reclaimed lands e.g. the port Island in Kobe (Japan), Rajorhat and Saltlake in Kolkata (India). Such structures are prone to liquefaction induced damages if subjected to dynamic loading (earthquakes). Structures on loose to medium dense sands are often provided pile foundations as the bearing soils are not stiff enough to support these structures. Failure of pile foundations was noticed in many cases and it was observed that even after the provision of large factor of safety against bending failure, structures often failed. In bending failure mechanism, lateral loads due to inertia and lateral spreading (slope

movement) induces bending in the piles. Earthquake exerts an abrupt dynamic loading and causes damage to structures both above and below the ground. It is very difficult to ascertain the failure mechanism of foundation of a structure without deep excavation. Twenty years after the Niigata earthquake 1964 and the Kobe earthquake 1995, investigations have been done to find the failure pattern of the piles. Piles were excavated from the subsoil, photographs of boreholes were taken, and pile integrity tests were carried out. These studies indicated the location of the cracks and damage patterns for the piles. Some of the observations are presented below:

1. The failure of foundations occurred in both laterally spreading grounds and level grounds. The failure pattern (tilting of buildings) is similar. This is shown in Fig 1.

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Fig.1. Building Failures after Kobe Earthquake (after Bhattacharya et al, 2013)

2. Cracks were observed near top and bottom boundaries of liquified and non liquified soil layers. Bhattacharya & Madabhushi (2008) observed the formation of plastic hinges at different depth of liquified and non liquified soil layers.

Fig. 2: SPT values describing variation of soil profile along the depth of pile

3. It has been observed that large diameter piles performed well during the seismic activity. For example, the older jetties of the Kandla port supported on R.C.C. piles of diameter 0.5 m suffered cracking during the Bhuj earthquake 2001, whereas in the same area, the RCC piles having 1.0 m diameter on the newer jetties performed well.

DIFFERENT TYPES OF FAILURE MECHANISMS FOR PILE SUPPORTED STRUCTURES IN LIQUEFIABLE SOILS

1. Bending failure mechanism: Bending failure generally occurs due to transverse or lateral seismic load or due to inertia of the superstructure. As the earthquake excitation begins, soil near the pile starts losing strength and flows in lateral direction, which is also responsible for the bending failure of the pile. Effect of this lateral flow of soil will be more in case of sloping ground called lateral spreading of the

ground. Bending in the pile due to lateral spreading of ground is often regarded as the root cause of many bridge failure.

2. Buckling failure mechanism: As the process of liquefaction progresses, confinement of pile by surrounding soil decreases to such a low value that the pile starts acting like a long slender column. Now, axial load coming from the superstructure will cause buckling and pile will not be able to support the superstructure load. Magnitude of buckling will depend upon the stiffness of the pile, depth of the liquefiable soil and magnitude of ground shaking during earthquakes.

3. Shear failure: This type of failure occurs due to lateral load such as kinematic or inertia load or combination of both. This type of failure is generally observed in hollow circular concrete piles having low shear strength capacity.

4. Settlement failure mechanism: Due to combined action of buckling and bending it may be possible that structure will settle vertical or it may tilt in one direction.

5. Dynamic failure mechanism: At the central pier of the river bridge, the depth of water increases in comparison to the water level near abutment and depth of embedment decreases and hence, the unsupported length of pier increases. This elongates the natural period for the central bridge pier as compared to the neighboring piers and abutment. Many bridge failures are attributed to collapse of central piers. The collapse of Showa Bridge (1964 Niigata earthquake) is considered to demonstrate this mechanism. Table 1 summarizes the list of various bridge failures due to liquefaction. Table 2 summarizes the performance review of various bridges situated in earthquake impacted locations.

Fig. 3: Various Failure Mechanism a) Kandla Port Building with pile foundation; b) shear failure; c) Bending failure; d) Buckling; e) Dynamic amplification (Bhattacharya et al., 2008)

Table 1. List of Bridge Failures due to Soil Liquefaction (Bhattacharya et al., 2017)

Earthquake Event	Bridge Name	Damage Type
Tohoku (2011)	Rokko Bridge	Mid span collapsed
Wenchuan (2008)	Miaoziping Bridge	One of the approaching spans collapsed
	Gaoyuancun Bridge	Mid span fell off the piers due to liquefaction
Costa Rica (1991)	Rio Viscaya Bridge	One internal supporting pier was missing
Philippines (1990)	Magsaysay Bridge	Piers settled and failed, and the bridge fell into the river
Tangshan (1976)	Zhuacun Bridge	The girders of the mid span collapsed
	Shahe Bridge	Bridge girder support collapsed
Philippines (1976)	Quirino Bridge	Mid span collapsed for the truss bridge
Haicheng (1975)	Panshan Bridge	One of the mid piers sank, causing collapse
Niigata (1964)	Showa Bridge	Few mid span collapsed

Table 2: Assessment of Performance of Various Pile Supported Bridges during Earthquakes (Source: Bhattacharya et al., 2004)

Case History and Reference	Pile section/ type	Performance	Case History and Reference	Pile section/ type	Performance
10 Storey Hokuriku Building, Hamada (1992a, b)	0.4 m dia RCC	Good	N.H.K Building, Hamada (1992a, b)	0.35 m dia RCC hollow	Poor
Landing Bridge, Berrill <i>et al.</i> (2001)	0.4 m square PSC	Good	NFCH Building, Hamada (1992a, b)	0.35 m dia RCC	Poor
14 Storey Building, Tokimatsu <i>et al.</i> (1996)	2.5 m dia RCC	Good	Yachiyo Bridge, Hamada (1992a, b)	0.3 m dia RCC	Poor
Hanshin Expressway pier, Ishihara (1997)	1.5 m dia RCC	Good	Gaiko Ware House, Hamada (1992a, b)	0.6 m dia PSC hollow	Poor
LPG Tank 101, Ishihara (1997)	1.1 m dia RCC		4 Storey fire house, Tokimatsu <i>et al.</i> (1996)	0.4 m dia PSC	Poor
Kobe Shimim hospital, Soga (1997)	0.66 m dia steel tube	Good	Showa Bridge, Hamada (1992a, b)	0.6 m dia steel tube	Poor

CASE STUDY OF DIFFERENT STRUCTURES DURING VARIOUS EARTHQUAKE

The case studies reported by Dash *et al.* (2012) have been reviewed and presented below:

1. *Failure of Customs Office Tower at Kandla (India)*: The Customs office tower at Kandla port is a six-floor building, 22 m in height and very close to the waterfront (Figure 4). This pile-supported tower tilted about 30 cm at its top during the Bhuj earthquake 2001. The building was founded on 32 short cast-in-situ concrete piles. Each pile was 0.4 m in diameter and 18m long. The piles were passing through clayey crust of 10 m depth and then terminated in a sandy soil layer. At this site, very little damage occurred in the super-structure, but considerable damage happened in the foundation. The analysis was carried out by applying the superstructure load and the lateral spreading simultaneously to investigate the combined response of lateral spreading and settlement.

Fig 4: Plausible settlement mechanism of failure showing the tilting the Tower, assuming there is no structural failure of piles.

2. *Failure of firehouse building in Kobe Port (Japan)*: Four-storey firehouse building at the foot of the Kobe O-Hashi Bridge on Port Island moved and tilted towards the sea during Kobe earthquake (1995). Bhattacharya (2006) studied this case history to understand the mechanism of its pile failure. The piles were axially loaded heavily (412 kN each) and were laterally unsupported for 16.4m of their length due to liquefied soil layer (Figure 5). The factor of safety against buckling for the piles was found to be 0.81. This suggests that the piles could probably have failed due to buckling at full liquefaction of the ground during the earthquake.

Fig. 5: Schematic of building's foundation failure during 1995 Kobe earthquake

3. *Failure of NHK Building in Niigata City (Japan)*: Four-storey R.C frame building supported over RC piles leaned during the Niigata earthquakes (1964). Widespread liquefaction and lateral spreading of the soil were observed near the building site due to which bending and dynamic amplification occurred.

CONCLUSION

The failure mechanism of pile foundation in soil, which is susceptible to liquefaction, is difficult to predict just based on surface observation. Engineers need to carry out detailed calculations. Similar type of surface observation is possible for different pile failure mechanisms. For example, bending, buckling, shear, uneven settlement and dynamic amplification of the pile group may lead to tilting or collapse of the superstructure. All the three structures studied in this paper were constructed on liquefied soils and tilted after the occurrence of a damaging earthquake, however the governing mechanism of their pile failure were very different. It is, however, important to recognize the failure mechanisms, which will govern the design of new foundations or retrofitting of existing foundations.

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